

Studies in Diphenyl Series. Part I. Synthesis of Unsymmetrical Derivatives of Diphenyl.

BY NRIPENDRANATH CHATTERJEE.

Hirsch prepared 4- and 2-hydroxydiphenyl by reacting the diazonium salt of benzene with phenol (*Ber*, 1890, 23, 3705).

The present paper describes an extension and modification of Hirsch's method for the synthesis of diphenyl derivatives. It involves the reaction of an aromatic diazonium salt with a phenol under conditions in which nitrogen is eliminated to yield a diphenyl derivative and a diphenyl ether as a by-product.

The solution of diazonium salt was added to a phenol at 95° and the reaction product was subjected to fractional distillation with superheated steam when the following fractions were obtained:

- (i) The first fraction consisting of the unreacted phenol.
- (ii) The second fraction consisting of the phenol ether.
- (iii) The third fraction consisting of a mixture of the phenol ether and the diphenyl derivative.
- (iv) The fourth fraction consisting of the pure diphenyl derivative.

As regards the constitution of the diphenyl derivatives the position of the methyl group (when toluidines were used) in one of the benzene ring is settled automatically from the nature of the aromatic amine used. The position of the two groups in the other ring will depend on the nature of the linking (either *para* or *ortho*) to the OH group. It was established as follows:

The methyl ether, obtained by means of dimethyl sulphate, was oxidised with neutral permanganate in the usual manner to methyl ethers of the corresponding acids (monobasic or dibasic) from which the carboxyl group was removed by heating with lime to give the known 2-methoxy- (A) and 4-methoxydiphenyl (B):

The compounds obtained from (*o*-, *m*-, *p*-) diazonium salt of toluene with cresols (*o*-, *m*-, *p*-) together with the oxidation products of their methoxy derivatives are given below :

Amine and phenol.	Diphenyls obtained.	Diphenyls obtained on oxidation.
<i>o</i> -Toluidine +		
<i>o</i> -Cresol.	4-Hydroxy-2' :3-dimethyl-	4-Methoxy-2' :3-dicarboxy-
<i>m</i> -Cresol.	4-Hydroxy-2' :2-dimethyl-	4-Methoxy-2' :2-dicarboxy-
<i>p</i> -Cresol.	2 Hydroxy-2' :5-dimethyl-	2-Methoxy-2' :5 dicarboxy-
<i>m</i> -Toluidine +		
<i>o</i> -Cresol.	4-Hydroxy-3' :3-dimethyl-	4-Methoxy-3' :3-dicarboxy-
<i>m</i> -Cresol.	4-Hydroxy-3' :2-dimethyl-	4-Methoxy-3' :2-dicarboxy-
<i>p</i> -Cresol.	2 Hydroxy-3' :5-dimethyl	2-Methoxy-3' :5-dicarboxy-
<i>p</i> -Toluidine +		
<i>o</i> -Cresol.	4-Hydroxy-3' :4'-dimethyl	4-Methoxy-3' :4'-dicarboxy-
<i>m</i> -Cresol.	4-Hydroxy-2 :4'-dimethyl-	4-Methoxy-2 :4'-dicarboxy-
<i>p</i> -Cresol.	2-Hydroxy-5 :4'-dimethyl-	2-Methoxy-5 :4'-dicarboxy-

The yields of the diphenyl derivatives are 10-15%. Of the phenyl-ethers prepared 3:4'-dimethyl-, 2:4'-dimethyl-, and 2:3'-dimethyl-phenyl ethers have been prepared for the first time. As the yield of the ethers in all the cases is high, it may be pointed out that this method is also equally suitable for the preparation of the compounds of this type.

Of the hydroxymethyldiphenyls described, only 4-hydroxy-3-methyldiphenyl is previously described in the literature (*Ber.*, 1922, 65, 1382), which was prepared from 3-methyldiphenyl by sulphonation and subsequent alkali fusion and there is no definite proof about the position of the OH group.

Though these diphenyl derivatives are not able to throw much light on the stereochemistry of the diphenyls, they are useful in another way. As the *pp'*-positions are definitely known to be occupied in some of them, these would on nitration or halogenation, cause the nitro or halogen group to be attached only at the *oo'*-position and as such would be more easily resolvable.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Decomposition of benzenediazonium sulphate with cresol (ortho).—The diazo compound was prepared by treating a cold solution of aniline sulphate (40 g. of aniline in 80 g. of sulphuric acid and 40 c.c. of water), with a solution of sodium nitrite (36 g.) in water (80 c.c.). The solution of diazo salt was then poured in small quantity with constant shaking to *o*-cresol (80 g.) heated to about 95°. A black oil separated and much nitrogen was evolved. The black oil was separated

and subjected to distillation in superheated steam and collected in four fractions :

(i) Temp. of the steam 120° , temp. of oil-bath containing the flask 115° —phenol and cresol.

(ii) Steam (150°), temp. of oil-bath (130°)—phenyl ether.

(iii) Steam (180°), temp. of oil-bath (160°)—mixture of the ethers and the diphenyl derivative,

(iv) Steam ($200-220^{\circ}$), temp of oil-bath (190°)—pure diphenyl derivative.

The *4-hydroxy-3-methyldiphenyl* was separated from phenyl ether by caustic alkali, the undissolved ether was removed by means of ether and the alkali solution was acidified. The separated diphenyl derivative was dissolved in ether, ether distilled off and it was then crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 114° . (Found: C, 84.5; H, 6.4. $C_{13}H_{12}O$ requires C, 84.7; H, 6.50 per cent).

Methylation of 4-hydroxy-3-methyldiphenyl.—It was dissolved in 10 % alkali, and dimethylsulphate (slight excess over the calculated amount) was added in small portion with constant shaking, and the reaction was completed on the water-bath. The methoxy derivative was extracted with ether, ether distilled off and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 76° . (Found: C, 84.6; H, 7.0. $C_{14}H_{14}O$ requires C, 84.8; H, 7.0 per cent).

Acetylation of 4-hydroxy-3-methyldiphenyl.—It was acetylated by refluxing for 3 hours with acetic anhydride in presence of a drop of pyridine. The reaction mixture was poured into water and the precipitate crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 83° . (Found: C, 79.0; H, 6.0. $C_{15}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 79.6; H, 6.1 per cent).

Oxidation of 4-methoxy-3-methyldiphenyl.—A concentrated solution of permanganate (1.6 g.) was added gradually to a suspension of the substance (1 g.) in boiling water (10 c.c.). It was then allowed to reflux till the permanganate was decolourised (12 to 15 hours), filtered and acidified. It was finally crystallised from dilute acetic acid, m.p. 172° . (Found: C, 73.4; H, 5.0. $C_{14}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 73.6; H, 5.2 per cent).

Decarboxylation of the acids.—The acid was heated with lime to 200° and the product was extracted with alcohol, from which on evaporation 4-methoxy- or 2-methoxydiphenyl crystallised out. Almost identical conditions and processes were employed in the preparation of the diphenyls and their derivatives, described in the following table.

Amine and phenol,	Products.	Formulae.	M.p. or B.p.	Found.	Req.	Found.	Req.	Remarks.
1. <i>o</i> -Toluidine + <i>o</i> -cresol	4-Hydroxy-3 : 2'-dimethyl diphenyl and 2 : 2'-Dimethylphenylether	$C_{14}H_{14}O$	160°/10 mm.	C, 84.6%	84.8%	H, 6.8%	7.0%	
The acetyl derivative		$C_{16}H_{16}O_2$	130°/10 mm.	79.8	80.0	6.4	6.6	
The methoxy derivative		$C_{15}H_{16}O$	125°/10 mm.	84.5	84.9	7.3	7.5	
Oxidation product of methoxy derivative	4-Methoxy-3 : 2'-dicarboxydiphenyl	$C_{15}H_{12}O_5$	210°	65.8	66.1	4.2	4.4	On heating with lime-4-methoxydiphenyl.
2. <i>m</i> -Toluidine + <i>o</i> -cresol	4-Hydroxy-3 : 3'-dimethyl diphenyl and 2 : 3'-Dimethylphenyl ether	$C_{14}H_{14}O$	175°/9 mm.	84.7	84.8	7.0	7.0	
The acetyl derivative		$C_{14}H_{14}O$	170°/17 mm.	84.7	84.8	6.9	7.0	
The methoxy derivative		$C_{16}H_{16}O_2$	158°/10 mm.	79.6	80.0	6.2	6.6	
Oxidation product of methoxy derivative	4-Methoxy-3 : 3'-dicarboxydiphenyl	$C_{15}H_{16}O$	150°/10 mm.	84.7	84.9	7.4	7.5	
3. <i>p</i> -Toluidine and <i>o</i> -cresol	4-Hydroxy-3 : 4'-dimethyl diphenyl and 2 : 4'-Dimethylphenylether	$C_{15}H_{12}O_5$	232°	66.0	66.1	4.4	4.4	On heating with lime 4-methoxydiphenyl.
The acetyl derivative		$C_{14}H_{14}O$	136°	84.5%	84.8%	7.1%	7.0%	
The methoxy derivative		$C_{14}H_{14}O$	180°/17 mm.	84.6	84.8	6.8	7.0	
Oxidation product of methoxy derivative	4-Methoxy-3 : 4'-dicarboxydiphenyl	$C_{16}H_{16}O_2$	74°	79.6	80.0	6.5	6.6	
The methoxy derivative		$C_{15}H_{16}O$	80°	84.5	84.9	7.1	7.5	On heating with lime 4-methoxydiphenyl.
Oxidation product of methoxy derivative		$C_{15}H_{12}O_5$	275°	65.7	66.1	4.2	4.4	

Amine and phenol.	Products.	Formulae.	M.p. or B.p.	Analytical data.				Remarks.
				Found.	Req.	Found.	Req.	
4. Aniline and <i>m</i> -cresol	4-Hydroxy-2-methyldiphenyl and 2-Methylphenylether	$C_{13}H_{12}O$	180°/15 mm.	C, 84.5%	84.7%	H, 6.2%	6.5%	
The acetyl derivative		$C_{15}H_{14}O_2$	168°/12 mm.	79.4	79.6	6.1	6.1	
The methoxy derivative		$C_{14}H_{14}O$	164°/12 mm.	81.6	84.8	6.6	7.0	On heating with lime 4-methoxydiphenyl.
Oxidation product of methoxy derivative	4-Methoxy-2-carboxydiphenyl	$C_{14}H_{12}O_3$	135°	73.3	73.6	5.1	5.2	
5. <i>o</i> -Toluidine + <i>m</i> -cresol.	4-Hydroxy-2,2'-dimethyldiphenyl and 2,3'-Dimethyldiphenyl ether.	$C_{14}H_{14}O$	185°/15 mm.	84.4	84.8	6.9	7.0	
The acetyl derivative.		$C_{14}H_{14}O$	170°/17 mm.	84.7	84.8	6.9	7.0	
The methoxy derivative.		$C_{16}H_{16}O_2$	175°/12 mm.	79.5	80	6.3	6.6	
Oxidation product of methoxy derivative,	4-Methoxy-2,2'-dicarboxydiphenyl.	$C_{15}H_{12}O_5$	210°	65.6	66.1	4.0	4.4	On heating with lime 4-methoxydiphenyl.
6. <i>m</i> -Toluidine + <i>m</i> -cresol.	4-Hydroxy-2,3'-dimethyldiphenyl and 3,3'-Dimethyldiphenylether	$C_{14}H_{14}O$	195°/15 mm.	84.6	84.8	6.6	7.0	
The acetyl derivative.		$C_{16}H_{16}O_2$	186°/15 mm.	79.7	80.0	6.9	6.6	

Analytical data.

Amine and phenol.	Products.	Formulae.	M.p. or B.p.	Found.	Req.	Found.	Req.	Remarks.
The <i>methoxy</i> derivative.		$C_{15}H_{16}O$	185°/15 mm.	C, 84.7%	84.9% H, 7.2%	4.4	4.4	On heating with lime 4-methoxydiphenyl.
Oxidation product of 4-Methoxy-2:3'-dicarboxydiphenyl		$C_{15}H_{12}O_5$	240°	66.0	66.4	4.4	4.4	On heating with lime 4-methoxydiphenyl.
7. <i>p</i> -Toluidine and <i>m</i> -cresol.	4-Hydroxy-2:4'-dimethyldiphenyl and 4':3-Dimethylphenylether	$C_{14}H_{14}O$ $C_{14}H_{14}O$	225°/15 mm. 175°/17 mm.	84.7 84.8	84.8 84.8	6.8 6.7	7.0 7.0	
The <i>acetyl</i> derivative.		$C_{16}H_{16}O_2$	210°/15 mm.	79.6	80.0	6.5	6.6	
The <i>methoxy</i> derivative.		$C_{15}H_{16}O$	205°/13 mm.	84.8	84.9	7.5	7.5	
Oxidation product of 4-Methoxy-2:4'-dicarboxydiphenyl		$C_{15}H_{12}O_5$	280°	65.9	66.1	4.1	4.4	On heating with lime 4-methoxydiphenyl.
8. <i>o</i> -Toluidine and <i>p</i> -cresol.	2-Hydroxy 2':5'-dimethyldiphenyl and 4':2-Dimethylphenylether	$C_{14}H_{14}O$ $C_{14}H_{14}O$	195°/14 mm. 180°/17 mm.	84.6 84.6	84.8 84.8	7.0 6.8	7.0 7.0	
The <i>acetyl</i> derivative.		$C_{16}H_{16}O_2$	186°/10 mm.	79.7	80.0	6.3	6.6	
The <i>methoxy</i> derivative.		$C_{15}H_{16}O$	185°/13 mm.	84.5	84.9	7.2	7.5	
Oxidation product of 2-Methoxy-5:2'-dicarboxydiphenyl		$C_{15}H_{12}O$	Does not melt below 300°.	65.9	66.1	4.3	4.4	On heating with lime 2-methoxydiphenyl.

Analytical data.

Amine and phenol.	Products.	Formulae.	M.p. or B.p.	Found.	Req.	Found.	Req.	Remarks.
9. <i>m</i> -Toluidine and <i>p</i> -cresol.	2-Hydroxy-5:3'-dimethyldiphenyl and 4':3-Dimethylphenylether	$C_{14}H_{14}O$ $C_{14}H_{14}O$	210°/14 mm. 175°/17 mm.	C, 84.6% 84.5	84.8% 84.8	H, 6.9% 6.7	7.0% 6.7	
The acetyl derivative.		$C_{16}H_{16}O_2$	204°/15 mm.	80.1	80.0	6.4	6.6	
The methoxy derivative.		$C_{15}H_{16}O$	200°/13 mm.	84.7	84.9	7.3	7.5	
Oxidation product of methoxy derivative.	2-Methoxy-5:3'-dicarboxydiphenyl	$C_{15}H_{12}O_5$	Does not melt below 300°	65.9	66.1	4.2	4.4	On heating with lime 2-methoxydiphenyl.
10. <i>p</i> -Toluidine and <i>p</i> -cresol.	2-Hydroxy-5:4'-dimethyldiphenyl 4:4'-Dimethylphenylether	$C_{14}H_{14}O$	225°/15 mm.	84.5	84.8	7.2	7.0	
The acetyl derivative.		$C_{16}H_{16}O_2$	215°/15 mm.	79.9	80.0	6.6	6.6	
The methoxy derivative.		$C_{15}H_{16}O$	205/42 mm.	84.5	84.9	7.9	7.5	
Oxidation product of methoxy derivative.	2-Methoxy-5:4'-dicarboxydiphenyl	$C_{15}H_{12}O_5$	Does not melt below 300°.	65.8	66.1	4.1	4.4	On heating with lime 2-methoxydiphenyl.

In conclusion, the author desires to express his thanks to Prof. Dr. P. C. Mitter for much encouragement and valuable advice during the course of this work.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE
AND TECHNOLOGY, CALCUTTA.

Received February 2, 1935.